

Impact of TRISO Packing Fraction and Spatial Distribution on SmAHTR Neutronic Behavior

C. A. M. Silva^{1,2}, G. L. Calegario¹, S. Gallardo^{2,3}, M. Lourduy-Alós³, G. Verdú^{2,3}, C. Pereira^{1,2}, A. L. Costa^{1,2,*}

¹Departamento de Engenharia Nuclear, Escola de Engenharia, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais, Av. Antonio Carlos 6627, Campus Pampulha, Belo Horizonte, MG, Brazil;

²Instituto Nacional de Ciências e Tecnologia de Reatores Nucleares Modulares e Inovadores/CNPq, Brazil;

³Instituto Universitario de Seguridad Industrial, Radiofísica y Medioambiental, Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera, s/n, 46022 València, València, Spain

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ABSTRACT

The present work evaluates how the packing fraction and spatial distribution of TRISO particles influence the neutronic behavior of the SmAHTR reactor. Several particle-packing configurations were examined to assess their effects on fuel-compact heterogeneity, moderation efficiency, and the corresponding changes in k_{inf} . The results indicate that packing fraction is the principal parameter governing the neutronic response of TRISO-based fuel compacts. Increasing the packing fraction reduces moderator volume, hardens the neutron-energy spectrum, and consequently decreases k_{inf} . For the same packing-fraction value, different TRISO-particle arrangements play a secondary role, except for the HCP configuration, where spatial ordering significantly alters the balance between thermal and fast fissions. Among the evaluated cases, the optimal packing fraction is 20% for SC, BCC, FCC, and SH, while HCP shows an optimum at 10%.

Keywords: SMR, SmAHTR, TRISO packing fraction, MCNP 6.2

1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) have attracted significant attention in recent years due to their potential for enhanced safety, flexible deployment, and reduced capital investment [1]. Among advanced SMR concepts, the Fluoride-Salt-Cooled Small Modular Advanced High-Temperature Reactor (SmAHTR) is a promising design that combines high-temperature operation with the inherent stability of a low-pressure fluoride-salt coolant [2]. SmAHTR employs a TRi-structural ISOtropic (TRISO)-based solid fuel and a graphite-moderated core to achieve improved thermal efficiency and robust passive safety, making it an appealing candidate for both electricity generation and industrial heat applications. TRISO fuel particles consist of a small fuel kernel surrounded by multiple ceramic coating layers—buffer carbon, pyrolytic carbon, and silicon carbide—that act as a miniature containment system [3]. This structure provides excellent fission-product retention, high-temperature tolerance, and strong resistance to irradiation, making TRISO fuel well-suited for advanced reactors. The TRISO particles are compacted with graphite to form cylindrical fuel pins. The packing fraction of TRISO particles determines the fuel density, thereby affecting the reactor's reactivity, heat generation, and safety. It is crucial for optimizing efficiency and thermal performance. In this sense, the present paper evaluates the sensitivity of the neutronic parameters due to variations in the packing fraction, aiming to assess their impact on the multiplication factor and neutron-energy spectrum. Accordingly, the packing fraction and spatial arrangement of the TRISO particles are systematically varied to assess their effect on the reactor's multiplication factor and neutron-energy spectrum. The MCNP 6.2 code was used for the calculations, and the methodology and simulation results are presented in the next sections.

* antonella@nuclear.ufmg.br

2. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1 illustrates the SmAHTR core, and Table I summarizes its principal design features. The reactor has a thermal power of 125 MW and an effective core lifetime of 4.19 years. SmAHTR uses low-enriched (19.75 wt %) uranium oxycarbide (UCO) as fuel, graphite as the moderator, and molten LiF–BeF₂ salt as the coolant. The active core consists of 19 identical hexagonal fuel assemblies, each containing 72 fuel pins and 19 graphite pins [2]. It is surrounded by a graphite reflector, which enhances neutron economy and sustains the chain reaction.

Figure 1. Geometric design of SmAHTR core.

Table I. Main features of SmAHTR core.

Variable	Value	Unity
Reactor power	125	MW(t)
Core volumetric power density	9.4	MW(t)/m ³
Primary coolant salt	FLiBe	
Fuel enrichment	19.75	wt %
Core uranium loading at BOC	1600 – 2020	kg
Core life	4.19	years
Moderator material	Graphite	
Moderator configuration	Pins and blocks	
Core height	4	m
Core effective diameter	~2.2	m
Reflector configuration and material	Radial, graphite blocks	
Effective reflector diameter (inside – outside)	~2.2 – 3	m

To minimize computational cost and streamline the modeling workflow, the simulations employ a single representative fuel assembly with reflective boundary conditions (Figure 2). Reference [2] provides the geometric and composition data. The UCO fuel is enriched to 19.75%, and the coolant (molten salt) is depleted in ^6Li —containing 99.995% ^7Li —because ^6Li strongly absorbs neutrons, which would otherwise contribute to sustaining the chain reaction [4]. Reducing the ^6Li content therefore improves neutron economy, lowers parasitic absorption, and supports more stable reactor operation, while maintaining the desired chemical and thermophysical properties of the salt. The physical densities of the fuel, graphite, and coolant are $10.40\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, $2.26\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, and $3.30\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, respectively. The physical densities of the TRISO layers are $1.05\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (carbon buffer), $1.90\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (pyrolytic carbon), $3.19\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (silicon carbide), and $1.90\text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$ (pyrolytic carbon). Table II presents the main features of the simulated fuel block.

Figure 2. Simulated model in MCNP 6.2

Table II. Main features of the simulated Fuel Block.

Variable		Value	Unity
Radius of TRISO layers	Fuel kernel	0.0250	cm
	Carbon buffer	0.0350	cm
	Pyrolytic carbon	0.0390	cm
	Silicon carbide	0.0425	cm
	Pyrolytic carbon	0.0465	cm
Fuel/Graphite pin radius		1.40	cm
Pins pitch distance		3.08	cm
Coolant channel radius		16.94	cm
Fuel Block	Apothem	22.5	cm
	Height	400	cm
Operational Temperature	Fuel	1200	K
	Moderator	1100	K
	Coolant	900	K
Material Type	Fuel	UCO	
	Moderator	Graphite	
	Coolant	LiF-BeF ₂	
Fuel enrichment		19.75 %	wt%

Within each fuel pin, the TRISOs are modeled across a range of packing fractions. In this approach, unit cells are constructed using square or hexagonal lattice geometries, each containing a specific number of TRISO particles arranged inside a geometric prism (either a cube or a hexagonal prism). Five lattice types are considered: Simple Cubic (SC), Body-Centered Cubic (BCC), Face-Centered Cubic (FCC), Simple Hexagonal (SH), and Hexagonal Close-Packed (HCP) (Figure 3). Each configuration places a different number of TRISO spheres within the prism, and the prism dimensions vary according to the prescribed packing fraction. Table III summarizes the main characteristics of the TRISO configurations and provides the relationships used to determine the prism dimensions. In these relations, the prism edge lengths (e) are expressed as functions of the TRISO outer radius (r_T) and the packing fraction (p_f). Since r_T is a fixed value (465 μm), the edge lengths for each configuration are uniquely determined once the packing fraction is specified.

Figure 3. Unit cell for TRISO lattice configurations in MCNP 6.2

Table III. Geometric features of unit cell for TRISO lattice configuration.

CASE	Number of TRISO particles	Maximum packing fraction value	Equation for prism calculation	
			Base edge	Lateral edge
SC	1	52%	$e = \left[\frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot \frac{1}{p_f} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot r_T$	
BCC	2	68%	$e = \left[\frac{8}{3} \pi \cdot \frac{1}{p_f} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot r_T$	
FCC	4	74%	$e = \left[\frac{16}{3} \pi \cdot \frac{1}{p_f} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}} \cdot r_T$	
SH	1	60%	$e_B = \left[\frac{4\sqrt{3}}{27} \pi \cdot \frac{1}{p_f} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot r_T$	$e_L = 2 \cdot r_T$
HCP	6	74%	$e_B = \left[\frac{2\sqrt{2}}{3} \pi \cdot \frac{1}{p_f} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \cdot r_T$	$e_L = \frac{4\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot r_T$

The MCNP model employs the operational SmaHTR temperatures—1200 K for the fuel, 1100 K for the graphite, and 900 K for the coolant—and uses the ENDF/B-VII data library.

The simulations consist of 300 active cycles with 100,000 neutron histories per cycle, preceded by 50 inactive cycles to allow for source convergence. These parameters were selected to strike a balance

between statistical accuracy and computational efficiency. The present study primarily evaluates k_{inf} and the neutron energy spectrum, and the results demonstrate consistent statistical behavior. Convergence of the source distribution was assessed using Shannon entropy analysis, which provides a quantitative measure of its spatial stability across successive cycles. The results exhibit relative uncertainties below 1%, indicating robust statistical convergence. For the calculated k_{inf} , the largest standard deviation is 13 pcm.

3. RESULTS

Figure 4 shows the behavior of k_{inf} as a function of the packing-fraction values. Although the SC, BCC, FCC, and SH configurations contain different numbers of TRISO particles within their respective unit cells, they exhibit very similar k_{inf} and therefore follow nearly identical curve profiles. This behavior is due to the nearly identical neutron-energy spectrum, which, in turn, produces very similar probabilities of inducing fission in the thermal and fast energy ranges. Figure 5 presents the standard deviation of the simulated cases, ranging from 11 to 13 pcm. The results are statistically consistent and sufficiently converged for the purposes of this study.

Figure 4. Infinite multiplication factor as a function of packing fraction.

Figure 5. Statistical uncertainties of the simulated cases.

Figure 6 exemplifies this behavior: it presents the neutron-energy spectra for the FCC and SH configurations, which display closely matching neutron-flux magnitudes and nearly identical spectrum profiles. Consequently, the corresponding percentage of fission occurring in the thermal and fast energy ranges is also nearly identical. Figure 7 further illustrates this trend, showing that the relative contributions of thermal and fast neutrons to the total fission rate remain essentially unchanged among the SC, BCC, FCC, and SH configurations.

Figure 6. Neutron energy spectrum for SH and CFC cases.

Figure 7. Percentage of fission in the thermal and fast energy range for the evaluated cases.

Furthermore, Figure 6 depicts a clear spectrum hardening as the packing fraction increases. As the number of TRISO particles rises, the moderator volume within the fuel compact reduces. With fewer neutron-moderator collisions available to slow neutrons down, the overall thermalization efficiency decreases, resulting in a neutron-energy spectrum that progressively shifts toward higher energies. Evidently, this behavior reduces the percentage of thermal fission and increases the fast fission (Figure 7), which provokes a progressive decrease in k_{inf} as the packing fraction increases. Indeed, the SC, BCC, FCC, and SH configurations consistently exhibit this trend for $p_f > 20\%$.

However, for $p_f < 20\%$, these configurations exhibit the opposite behavior, with k_{inf} increasing as p_f increases (Figure 4). In the range $10\% < p_f < 20\%$, the addition of more TRISO particles produces the most pronounced spectrum hardening, which likely increases the percentage of fast-fissions (Figure 7) and may contribute to an enhancement of k_{inf} .

The HCP configuration shows a continuous decrease in k_{inf} across the entire p_f range, due to the gradual reduction in moderator volume, as previously explained. However, HCP stands out among the evaluated cases: it shows the highest k_{inf} at $p_f = 10\%$ and, in the interval $20\% < p_f < 60\%$, exhibits the smallest k_{inf} values (Figure 4).

Comparing HCP with the other configurations, the hardest neutron-energy spectrum occurs at $p_f = 10\%$. Figure 8 presents the spectrum profiles for FCC and HCP, illustrating this trend: HCP shows lower peaks in the thermal-energy range than FCC, with the largest difference at $p_f = 10\%$ (HCP-10 and FCC-10). Consequently, at $p_f = 10\%$, HCP has the smallest percentage of fissions in the thermal-energy range (Figure 7). Conversely, it has the highest fission rate in the fast-energy range, which could contribute to the highest k_{inf} at $p_f = 10\%$.

For $20\% < p_f < 60\%$, the harder neutron spectrum reduces the percentage of fissions in the thermal range (Figure 7), thereby lowering k_{inf} values. Although the percentage of fissions in the fast-energy range is higher and contributes to the total fission reactions, it does not result in k_{inf} values equal to or higher than those of the SC, BCC, FCC, and SH configurations.

Figure 8. Neutron energy spectrum for CFC and HPC cases.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In general, for the same packing fraction, different distributions of TRISO particles have little effect on the reactor's neutronic behavior. The SC, BCC, FCC, and SH configurations exhibit very similar k_{inf} trends due to nearly identical neutron energy spectra. The evaluated parameters are primarily governed by the packing fraction rather than by the specific number of TRISO particles in the unit cell. For packing fractions above 20%, spectrum hardening reduces thermal fissions, thereby decreasing k_{inf} values across all evaluated cases. Based on the calculated parameters, the optimum packing fraction for SC, BCC, FCC, and SH is 20%.

However, at the lowest TRISO density, the HCP configuration behaves differently, reaching the highest k_{inf} at $p_f = 10\%$. In this sense, HCP demonstrates the most efficient fuel utilization, since it achieves the highest k_{inf} value at a lower TRISO density.

Nevertheless, it is important to evaluate whether lower packing fractions can still ensure reactor criticality throughout the operational cycle, since SMR concepts such as SmAHTR are designed without

intermediate fuel reloading. Previous references cite a packing fraction of 50% [4][5][6], but such a high density may not be necessary, or even desirable, given the neutronic behavior observed in the present analysis. Higher packing fractions lead to stronger spectrum hardening, which reduces the contribution of thermal fissions and consequently lowers k_{inf} .

Moreover, excessively dense fuel regions may introduce additional thermal-hydraulic challenges without providing significant reactivity benefits. Therefore, establishing whether lower packing fractions can sustain criticality throughout the full operational cycle is essential.

This highlights the importance of identifying an optimal balance between fuel density, neutronic behavior, and long-term burnup capability. While lower packing fractions may initially yield higher k_{inf} values and more favorable neutron spectra, they must also provide sufficient excess reactivity to compensate for fuel depletion, fission-product buildup, and evolving spectrum effects throughout the reactor's lifetime. Consequently, the evaluation of packing-fraction impacts cannot be restricted to fresh-fuel conditions; it must also include full-cycle burnup simulations to ensure that the reactor remains critical under operating scenarios.

Furthermore, although the present study provides insights into the influence of packing fraction on reactor criticality, the analysis is restricted to the neutronic behavior of a representative SmAHT fuel block. From a full-core perspective, neutron interactions among fuel blocks and with the radial and axial reflectors are expected to reduce neutron energy, thereby modifying the neutron energy spectrum and affecting key neutronic parameters.

Accordingly, future work will focus on full-core simulations of the SmAHTR over the entire operational cycle, assessing the impact of different packing fractions on long-term reactivity behavior, fuel depletion, and overall cycle length. These analyses will enable a more robust determination of the minimum packing fraction required to meet performance and safety criteria throughout the core's lifetime.

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REFERENCES

- [1] IAEA. *Technology Roadmap for Small Modular Reactor Deployment*. International Atomic Energy Agency, Vienna, Austria (2021).
- [2] S. R. Greene, J. C. Gehin, D. E. Holcomb, J. J. Carbajo, D. Ilas, A. T. Cisneros, V. K. Varma, W. R. Corwin, D. F. Wilson, G. L. Yoder, Jr. A. L. Qualls, F. J. Peretz, G. F. Flanagan, D. A. Clayton, E. C. Bradley, G. L. Bell, J. D. Hunn, P. J. Pappano, M. S. Cetiner. *Pre-conceptual Design of a Fluoride-Salt-Cooled Small Modular Advanced High-Temperature Reactor (SmAHTR)*. Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, Tennessee, United States of America (2010).
- [3] B.E. Wells, N. R. Phillips, K. J. Geelhood. *TRISO Fuel: Properties and Failure Modes*. U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission. Office of Nuclear Regulatory Research. Washington, United States of America (2021).
- [4] D. Hartanto, G. Radulescu, F. Bostelmann, W. Wieselquist. *SCALE Analyses of Scenarios in the Molten Salt Reactor Fuel Cycle*. Oak Ridge National Laboratory. Oak Ridge, Tennessee, United States of America (2025).
- [5] K. L. Reed, F. Rahnema. "A Simplified SmAHTR Benchmark Problem Set." In *Proceedings of PHYSOR-2020*. EPJ Web of Conferences 247, 10023 (2021).
- [6] K. L. Reed, F. Rahnema, D. Zhang, D. Ilas. "A Stylized 3-D Benchmark Problem Set Based on the Pin-Fueled SmAHTR." *Nuclear Technology*, **volume 206**, issue 11, pp. 1686–1697 (2020).